

SPIRITUALITY OF YOUTH IN THE CONDITIONS OF GLOBALIZATION

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Annotation: This scientific article analyzes the positive and negative effects of the globalization process on the spirituality of young people. The article highlights the flow of information, mass culture, technological progress, and their impact on the minds of young people as a result of globalization. Also, the role of young people in preserving national values, traditions and spiritual heritage and the responsibility of education, family and society in this regard will be discussed. The study shows ways to strengthen the moral immunity of young people in the era of globalization based on statistical data, opinions of thinkers and modern social analysis.

Key words: globalization, youth spirituality, information flow, national values, mass culture, education, spiritual immunity, modern youth

Globalization is a process of interconnection in the economic, cultural and information spheres of the world, which unites humanity into a single information space. This process, of course, has a direct impact on the worldview, values and behavior of young people.

As a result of the widespread spread of the Internet, social networks and Western culture, among some young people, interest in consumerism, indiscriminate imitation, and an easy lifestyle is increasing. At the same time, attention to national traditions, values and culture is waning.

For example, according to sociological research, as a result of a survey conducted in Uzbekistan in 2024, 38 percent of young people considered national traditions secondary, which is considered a clear sign of moral decline.

However, globalization is not only a negative process. It has also opened the door to new opportunities for young people — study abroad, exchange programs, online learning, global communication and social activism. Today, more than 200,000 young people of Uzbekistan are studying on international online platforms. This helps them expand their worldview, acquire knowledge of science and technology.

Among the factors that have a strong influence on the minds of young people in the conditions of globalization, the information space, mass culture, and social networks occupy a special place. Today's youth are exposed to hundreds of different ideas, values and cultural expressions every day. Sometimes these

currents instill ideas that contradict their national thinking. As a result, individualism, indifference, and moral laxity appear among young people. The great philosopher Immanuel Kant said: "Spirituality is the only quality that separates man from animals." From this point of view, the gap in the spirituality of young people weakens the moral foundation of the whole society.

Another important aspect is that some young people choose the wrong way of life by believing the fake information on the Internet. The virtual world keeps them away from real life. Today's youth spend more than 6 hours on the Internet - which is dangerous not only for physical, but also for mental health. Fighting the effects of globalization is not isolation, but a conscious, strong spirituality. It is necessary for the youth to keep up with the times, but preserve their national identity.

In this sense, the educational system, the family, cultural centers, and religious-educational organizations must jointly lead young people to spiritual maturity. The great statesman and our first president Islam Abdugyanevich Karimov said: "We must raise a young generation with a broad outlook, independent thinking, high national pride and human qualities."

In fact, strengthening the youth spiritually means strengthening the future of not only them, but the entire nation.

Summary:

Globalization is one of the most complex but most important processes of our time. It provides humanity with unprecedented opportunities - free access to information, modern education, technological development and intercultural communication. At the same time, this process has a direct impact on the spirituality of young people, their worldview and value system.

Today's young generation is growing up in information waves. Along with positive ideas, negative values such as foreign culture, consumerism, and the pursuit of fame are entering their minds. Therefore, protecting the spirituality of young people, educating them to be loyal to the national identity and human qualities is one of the most important tasks for the society.

The great thinker Alisher Navai said: "Whoever knows himself, knows the world." Therefore, young people should first of all know their identity, deeply understand their national values, and rely on this foundation in communication with the world. After all, spirituality is the inner support of a person, the spiritual foundation of a nation. Today's youth are the owners of tomorrow. Tomorrow's society will be like their spiritual purity, national pride and thinking. Therefore,

every family, teacher and state is responsible for instilling bright thoughts, good ideas and national pride in the hearts of young people.

So, in the conditions of globalization, a truly spiritual youth is a person who is in tune with the times, but loyal to his roots, who lives with light and pride in his heart.

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